

Investigation of the Functional Properties of Some *Origanum* Species and Their Bioactive Components

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Abstract

The genus *Origanum* is represented by 24 species in Turkey, with an endemism rate of 63%. The chemical compositions of essential oils obtained through hydro distillation from thyme species such as *Origanum vulgare*, *Origanum onites*, and *Origanum minutiflorum*, collected from various locations in the Aegean and Mediterranean regions, were determined by using GC-MS analysis. Furthermore, the antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of the essential oils were investigated. Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis revealed that the major components of *O. minutiflorum* essential oils were carvacrol (67.86–84.95%), p-cymene (5.36–8.77%), and γ -terpinene (0.99–3.46%). In the case of *O. onites* essential oils, the major components were identified as carvacrol (30.01–71.96%), thymol (1.53–38.25%), p-cymene (3.90–10.07%), and γ -terpinene (2.25–5.07%). In the essential oil composition of *O. vulgare* samples collected from Alanya, the main components were found to be carvacrol (81.35%), linalool (10.17%), p-cymene (1.27%), thymol (1.21%), and β -caryophyllene (1.01%). For the purpose of antioxidant activity studies, the DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) free radical scavenging activity assay was employed. Utilizing the DPPH method, the EC₅₀ values of the investigated *Origanum* spp. were determined to range from 0.44 to 16.21 μ L, with the lowest value observed for *O. onites* (0.44 μ L) and the highest for *O. vulgare* (16.21 μ L). Furthermore, essential oils at varying concentrations (5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, and 80 μ L mL⁻¹) were mixed with bacterial suspensions and plated in petri dishes to determine the number of surviving bacteria. The results indicated that *Origanum* essential oils exhibited strong antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 and significantly reduced the numbers of *Listeria monocytogenes* (P<0.05).

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1. Introduction

The genus *Origanum*, which is of significant commercial value and is extensively exported, is represented by 23 species and 32 taxa in Turkey (Oflaz et al., 2002). Globally, *Origanum* species are represented by approximately 50 species, predominantly distributed in the Mediterranean region and the Balkans (Davis, 1982). The essential oils obtained from these species exhibit a variety of chemical and aromatic properties, in addition to possessing therapeutic effects such as choleric and antimicrobial activities. These oils find application in a wide range of industries, including agriculture, the pharmaceutical and cosmetics industries, food flavoring, alcoholic beverages, perfumery, and the soap industry. In addition to their commercial applications, *Origanum* spp. are renowned for their therapeutic benefits, particularly in the treatment of digestive and respiratory ailments. These species possess a range of pharmacological properties, including antiseptic, antispasmodic, carminative, diaphoretic, and expectorant effects, making them valuable therapeutic agents (Kılıç and Bağcı, 2008). *O. onites* that is the most exported one of five commercially traded species of *Origanum* in Turkey. This species contains 1–5% essential oil and is popularly referred to as "bilyalı kekik" (round thyme) in Turkish due to its small, spherical, umbrella-like flowers. This species is widely utilized and holds significant economic value and is referred to as "kekik" in Turkish. It is employed as a spice and in various forms for treating illnesses (Baytop, 1991). Another economically valuable species, *O. vulgare* subsp. *hirtum*, is also exported and is known in Europe as "Greek Oregano" and locally in Turkey as "Istanbul thyme" or "Çanakkale thyme" (Karaman and Özdemir, 2012). It is widely distributed in regions such as Thrace, Western and Southern Anatolia, Ege, Aegean, and Mugla (Karakaya and Özdemir, 2015). *O. vulgare* subsp. *hirtum* is a perennial plant with a strong aroma, white or pink flowers, a tubular calyx with five toothed lobes, and a height of 50–80 cm. It blooms in July and August (Karik

et al., 2007). In the global thyme market, *O. minutiflorum* O. Schwarz et H. Davis, also known as "Sütçüler thyme," "Yayla thyme," or "Toka thyme," is an endemic species found exclusively in the mountainous regions of Isparta, Turkey (Özhatay and Atay, 1997). This species is heavily harvested in the wild and exported. However, the ongoing uncontrolled and intensive harvesting of this species has led to a significant decline in its population density, classifying it as one of the top 10 most critically endangered species in Turkey, necessitating urgent conservation measures (Özhatay and Atay, 1997). Turkey is a country with a rich plant biodiversity, and the increasing interest in herbal remedies is attributed to their lack of side effects, the multiple benefits they offer, and their affordability (Çoban, 2007). For this reason, it is intended to investigate the chemical compositions, antioxidant and antimicrobial effects of *Origanum* spp., which are widely used in traditional practices and collected from various regions of Turkey. By scientifically validating these effects, it is hoped to expand the understanding of these plants. As the use of natural additives in the food industry grows, interest in plant-derived natural antioxidants is steadily increasing worldwide. Therefore, plants and spices have become a major focus of research for studying natural antioxidants. Detailed and multifaceted studies of these plants will provide significant health benefits and economic advantages for the country, particularly in terms of public health. The failure of antibiotics to combat disease-causing bacteria in edible plants has further underscored the necessity for antimicrobial agents derived from natural sources. The present study aims to analyze the compositions of essential oils obtained through the hydro distillation method from species such as *O. vulgare*, *O. onites*, and *O. minutiflorum*, collected from different regions using the GC-MS technique. Additionally, it seeks to determine the effects of major bioactive compounds identified in these compositions on the antioxidant and antimicrobial activity levels of the plants' essential oils.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Material

The plant materials employed in this study (*O. vulgare*, *O. onites*, and *O. minutiflorum*) consist of three species, some of which are endemic, collected from the Aegean (Muğla, Kaş) and Mediterranean (Antalya, Alanya) regions. The collected plants were cleaned, dried, and ground to reduce their size for distillation. Prior to analysis, the samples were

stored in polyethylene zip-lock bags under cool and dark conditions. Prior to this stage, all plant materials utilized in the study were subjected to grinding in order to reduce their particle size. The hydro distillation method was then employed to extract the essential oils, which were subsequently prepared for chromatographic analyses to determine their composition. The codes assigned to the prepared samples are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Origin of plant samples and the assigned codes for the plants

Plant	Origin	Code
<i>Origanum minutiflorum</i>	Alanya	OMA-345
<i>Origanum onites</i>	Alanya	OOA-711
<i>Origanum vulgare</i>	Alanya	OVA-993
<i>Origanum minutiflorum</i>	İnan Tarım-Antalya	OMA-126
<i>Origanum onites</i>	İnan Tarım-Antalya	OOA-465
<i>Origanum onites</i>	Ege	OOE-414
<i>Origanum minutiflorum</i>	Altes Tarım-Alanya	OMA-671
<i>Origanum onites</i>	Altes Tarım-Alanya	OOA-748
<i>Origanum minutiflorum</i>	Kaş-Ege	OME-982

2.2. Essential oil extraction

For plants with a high essential oil content, the Clevenger apparatus, a glass device, is used for steam distillation. This method involves heating a specific amount of plant material (the amount may vary depending on the size of the glass flask used) in water under controlled conditions for 2-3 hours, allowing the essential oil to be released. The steam carrying the essential oil is then condensed in a cooling system and collected in a specific location (Rasooli and Mirmostafa, 2003). In order to facilitate this process, 70 grams of dried plant material were placed within the Clevenger apparatus flask, with 500 mL of distilled water subsequently added. The temperature of the device was set to 350 °C, and the plant material was extracted by steam distillation for a period of approximately 3 hours. The essential oils thus obtained were collected and transferred into dark, air-tight bottles, whereafter they were stored in the dark at +4 °C.

2.3. Determination of essential oil composition

In this study, the analysis of the compounds presents in the essential oils obtained was

performed using a Shimadzu GCMS-QP2010+ gas chromatography device (Shimadzu, Columbia, USA). A 30 µL sample of the essential oil obtained by steam distillation was dissolved in 1.5 mL of hexane. Sodium sulfate was added to remove any water droplets present, and the sample was then introduced into the device. The compounds were identified using mass spectrometry (QP 2010+). For library searching, the FFNSC 1.3 (Flavor and Fragrance Natural and Synthetic Compounds) Aroma Index Library Retention Index was used, and retention times were calculated using a C₇-C₃₀ Alkanes Standard. The system incorporated a mass selective detector and a TBR-5MS GC column (30 m in length, with an inner diameter of 0.25 mm and a film thickness of 0.25 µm). The gas chromatography column oven was initially set to 40 °C, where it was maintained for two minutes. Thereafter, it was ramped up to 230 °C at a rate of 4 °C min⁻¹. The column temperature was maintained at 40 °C, while the injector temperature was set to 250 °C. A 1 µL injection was executed in split mode, with a pressure of 90 kPa, a total flow rate of 28.8 mL min⁻¹, and a split ratio of 15. Helium was utilized as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 1.61

mL min⁻¹. The identification and quantification of the separated compounds were performed using the relevant standard substances. The MS operating conditions are outlined in Table

2. The ion source temperature was set at 200 °C, the interface temperature at 250 °C, and the solvent cut time at 2.5 minutes.

Table 2. GC-MS Conditions

Equipment/Parameter	Description
Gas Chromatography	Shimadzu; Shimadzu Scientific Instruments 7102 Riverwood Drive, Columbia, U.S.A.
Detector	Mass Spectrometry
Mass Spectrometer	QP 2010 Plus
Column	TBR 5MS GC Column (30m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm)
Carrier Gas	Helium
Carrier Gas Flow Rate	1.61 mL min ⁻¹
Column Temperature	40 °C
Injector Temperature	250 °C
Initial Peak Pressure	90 kPa
Injection Mode	Split
Injection Volume	1 µL
Oven Temperature Program	Rate Temperature Hold Time (minutes) 4.0 230 °C 0 (Analysis time: 49.5 min)
MS Operating Conditions	
Ionization Mode	EI (Electron Impact)
MS Source Temperature	200 °C
Electron Energy	70 eV
Ion Source Temperature	200 °C
Interface Temperature	250 °C

2.4. The determination of antioxidant activity method

The DPPH method is utilized for the determination of antioxidant activity. This method is based on the reduction of the purple-colored stable compound DPPH radical through its reaction with the test compound. This results in a color change (from purple to yellow) that is measured at a wavelength of 517 nm using a spectrophotometer. When the intensely purple DPPH radical solution is mixed with an antioxidant-containing extract, the antioxidant reduces the radical. This reduction process leads to a change in color, with the intense purple shade of the DPPH solution (DPPH) being reduced to a yellow color (reduced DPPH) (Molyneux, 2004). Essential oil solutions at varying concentrations, prepared by diluting with methanol, were subjected to an incubation period of 30 minutes following the addition of 5 mL of a DPPH solution that had been prepared in methanol. The absorbances of the

samples were measured at a wavelength of 517 nm against a control sample (Cuendet et al., 1997). Preparation of 1 mM DPPH Radical Solution: In order to prepare 100 mL of a 1 mM radical solution, 0.03943 g of DPPH was weighed, dissolved in a small amount of methanol, and transferred quantitatively to a 100 mL volumetric flask. The solution was then diluted to volume with methanol, yielding a 1 mM DPPH radical solution. This solution was prepared fresh daily, wrapped in aluminum foil to protect it from light, and stored in a dark environment at +4 °C when not in use. For analysis, 25 mL of this stock radical solution was diluted to 50 mL with pure methanol. During the analysis, 2.5 mL of sample extracts obtained from plants, as previously described, were diluted to 25 mL (dilution factor = 10). Six test tubes were prepared with varying volumes of the diluted sample, and the DPPH solution mentioned earlier was added accordingly. The sample and DPPH solution volumes are presented in Table 3. Following the mixing stage, the tubes were

subjected to an incubation period in the dark at room temperature for a duration of 15 minutes. At the conclusion of the incubation period, the absorbance values of both the sample tubes and the control tubes were measured at a wavelength of 517 nm using a spectrophotometer. Utilizing the control's

measured value, the percentage inhibition corresponding to nine distinct sample volumes was calculated (Yen and Duh, 1994, Ellnain-Wojtaszek et al., 2003, Abdilla et al., 2005).

Table 3. Contents of test tubes in the determination of antioxidant activity by DPPH

1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	Control
600 µL DPPH	600 µL DPPH	600 µL DPPH	600 µL DPPH	600 µL DPPH	600 µL DPPH
20 µL sample	40 µL sample	60 µL sample	80 µL sample	100 µL sample	—
5380µL MeOH	5360µL MeOH	5340µL MeOH	5320µL MeOH	5300µL MeOH	5400µL MeOH

The percentage (%) inhibition values of the essential oil and standards were calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = (A_{\text{DPPH}}^* - A_{\text{extract}}^{**}) / A_{\text{DPPH}} \times 100$$

* A_{DPPH} : DPPH* The absorbance value of the control sample

** A_{extract} : The absorbance value of control extract

The EC50 value (the concentration required to inhibit 50% of the radical) was calculated using the equation derived from the inhibition curve. In the calculation, the dilution process applied to the sample was also considered. In the resulting graphs, the value of 50% was substituted for the "% inhibition" value (y), and the sample volume required to achieve 50% inhibition of the radical was determined and divided by the dilution factor (D_f).

$$\% \text{ Inhibition (y)} = \mathbf{a. (sample value) + b}$$

$$50 = [a \cdot (\text{sample value}) + b] / D_f$$

2.5. The determination of antimicrobial activity

2.5.1. Preparation of microorganism cultures for analysis

One-day-old cultures of the test microorganisms, *E. coli* O157:H7 and *L. monocytogenes* strains, were activated in Nutrient Broth (NB) and then serially diluted with 0.1% peptone water after an overnight incubation. From this series, 0.1 mL was taken from the 10^{-2} dilution (containing approximately 10^7 CFU mL^{-1} bacteria) to

evaluate the efficacy of the essential oils. From the same series, 0.1 mL samples were taken from the 10^{-6} and 10^{-7} dilutions (containing approximately 1.000 and 100 CFU, respectively) to determine the inoculation levels. These samples were then spread evenly on pre-poured petri dishes containing approximately 10–15 mL McConkey Sorbitol Agar (MCSA) for *E. coli* O157:H7 and 10–15 mL Oxford Agar for *L. monocytogenes*. The samples were spread evenly on the agar surface using a Drigalski spatula. Following the absorption of the samples by the medium, the petri dishes were placed into an incubator set at a temperature of 35 ± 2 °C for a period of 24–48 hours.

2.5.2. Essential oil concentrations

For the antimicrobial activity assay, a series of test tubes containing essential oil concentrations of 0 (control), 5, 20, 40, 60, and 80 $\mu\text{L mL}^{-1}$ (six tubes in total) were prepared. Each tube was first filled with 900 μL of 0.1% peptone water, followed by the addition of 100 μL of activated *E. coli* O157:H7 and *L. monocytogenes* cultures. Subsequently, essential oils at the specified concentrations were added to the respective tubes. To ensure proper mixing of the oil and water phases, 0.5% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was added, after which the mixture was vortexed at 2,500 rpm for 5 seconds. Serial dilutions were then prepared for each concentration using 0.1% peptone water, and control samples were prepared in the same manner but without the addition of essential oils.

2.5.3. Measurement of the inactivation effects of essential oils for determining antibacterial activity

In this study, cultures of *E. coli* O157:H7 and *L. monocytogenes* stored under refrigeration on slant agar were transferred to Nutrient Broth and activated at 35 ± 2 °C for 12–15 hours. The activated cultures were then used for antimicrobial activity assays. Following serial dilutions from the tubes containing essential oils and control tubes, the selected dilutions were plated using the spread plate method. A volume of 0.1 mL from each dilution was transferred onto pre-prepared petri dishes containing approximately 15 mL of MCSA and Oxford Agar. Each dilution was plated onto at least three petri dishes. The inoculated plates were then incubated at 35 ± 2 °C for 24–48 hours. Following this, the colony counts on the plates were recorded. The results were then converted to a \log_{10} scale, and the inoculation levels and antibacterial effects of the essential oils were calculated as \log CFU/mL.

2.6. Statistical analysis

The data underwent a descriptive statistical evaluation, whereby the mean and standard deviation of the results from three replicates performed on plants obtained from different locations were calculated. Two-way ANOVA was used to analyze the data at an alpha level of 0.05, with Minitab version 15 being used for this purpose.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Distribution of volatile aromatic compounds

In this study, nine distinct plant samples from three species—*Origanum onites*,

Origanum minutiflorum, and *Origanum vulgare*—collected from various locations were analyzed. The essential oils of these samples were obtained through hydro distillation from the aerial parts of the plant material. The chemical compositions of the essential oils were determined using GC-MS, revealing that the main components are phenolic monoterpenes, monoterpene hydrocarbons, oxygenated monoterpenes, aromatic hydrocarbons, and sesquiterpenes. The essential oil of *O. minutiflorum* was found to contain carvacrol (67.86–84.95%), p-cymene (5.36–8.77%), and γ -terpinene (0.99–3.46%) as the major components. Other components included linalool, isoborneol, and β -caryophyllene, with thymol content ranging between 0.25–0.63%. Among the *O. minutiflorum* species, the highest levels of carvacrol (84.95%) and thymol (0.63%) were identified in the essential oil coded OMA-671, obtained from plants collected in Alanya. The essential oil of *O. onites* was found to contain carvacrol (30.01–71.96%), thymol (1.53–38.25%), p-cymene (3.90–10.07%), and γ -terpinene (2.25–5.07%), as determined by GC-MS analysis. Other significant components included β -bisabolene, linalool, isoborneol, and β -caryophyllene. Among the *O. onites* species, the highest carvacrol content (71.96%) was found in the essential oil coded OOA-711, obtained from plants collected in Alanya. The highest thymol content (38.25%) was found in the essential oil coded OOE-414, obtained from *O. onites* plants cultivated in the Aegean region. In the analyses conducted, the essential oil coded OVA-993, obtained from *O. vulgare* plants collected in Alanya, was found to contain 81.35% carvacrol, 10.17% linalool, 1.27% p-cymene, 1.21% thymol, and 1.01% β -caryophyllene.

Table 4. Distribution results of aroma components by *Origanum varieties*

Aromatic Compound	OMA 126	OMA 345	OMA 671	OVA 993	OOA 711	OOA 465	OOA 748	OOE 414	OME 982
α Thujene	0.72	0.88	0.17	0.06	0.13	0.10	0.13	0.53	0.65
α Pinene	1.10	1.03	0.20	0.13	0.62	0.49	0.36	0.78	0.73
Camphene	0.83	0.51	0.06	-	0.28	0.29	0.16	0.58	0.38
β Pinene	0.22	0.25	0.06	-	0.08	0.08	0.05	0.12	0.18
Vinyl amyl carbinol	0.29	0.18	0.26	-	0.16	0.15	0.17	0.47	0.18
Myrcene	1.12	1.23	0.66	0.20	1.50	0.71	0.62	1.43	0.94
Ethyl hexanol	0.06	-	0.10	-	-	-	-	-	-
α Phellandrene	0.17	0.18	0.06	-	0.24	0.13	0.10	0.19	0.14
Carene	0.05	0.09	0.03	-	0.08	0.04	-	0.07	0.06
α Terpinene	1.08	1.03	0.57	0.23	1.50	0.81	0.86	1.67	0.79
Cymene (para)	7.40	8.77	5.36	1.27	5.67	3.90	5.03	10.07	6.64
β Ocimene	0.53	0.64	0.29	-	0.51	0.34	0.23	0.57	0.48
Eucalyptol	0.53	0.63	0.25	-	-	0.20	0.12	0.06	0.55
γ Terpinene	3.46	2.25	0.99	0.34	5.07	0.03	2.64	4.39	1.94
Sabinene hydrate	0.90	0.26	-	0.11	0.16	0.24	-	0.45	0.94
Terpinolene	0.24	0.29	0.08	-	0.25	0.22	0.12	0.21	0.22
Linalool	3.48	0.58	0.20	10.17	1.10	8.17	4.36	2.57	0.55
Isoborneol	2.61	1.51	0.49	0.44	1.50	1.79	1.26	3.01	1.41
Terpinen-4-ol	1.05	1.18	1.92	0.65	1.08	1.05	1.09	1.84	1.11
α Terpineol	0.35	0.36	0.67	0.66	0.24	0.32	0.19	0.31	0.34
Carvone	0.13	-	0.12	0.12	0.16	0.15	0.06	0.07	-
Thymol	0.54	0.25	0.63	1.21	1.53	2.11	27.17	38.25	0.29
Carvacrol	67.86	72.46	84.95	81.35	71.96	69.13	52.01	30.01	76.33
β Caryophyllene	2.28	2.04	0.45	1.01	1.35	1.81	-	0.30	2.07
Aromadendrene	0.32	0.30	0.10	0.22	0.18	0.29	0.68	0.06	0.30
Humulene	0.09	0.09	-	-	-	0.11	-	-	-
Viridiflorene	0.21	0.18	0.06	0.17	0.12	0.19	0.13	-	0.19
β Bisabolene	0.18	0.16	-	-	2.33	2.27	0.12	0.10	0.18
Spathuneol	0.14	0.18	0.09	-	0.16	0.26	0.15	0.09	0.22
Caryophyllene oxide	0.24	0.26	0.17	0.13	0.30	0.39	0.24	0.12	0.31

Amongst all *Origanum* spp., the highest carvacrol content was recorded in *O. minutiflorum* (OMA-671) collected from Alanya, with a ratio of 84.95%, whilst the lowest carvacrol content was identified in *O. onites* (OOE-414) collected from the Aegean region, with a ratio of 30.01%. The plant with the highest thymol content (38.25%) was *O. onites* (OOE-414) collected from the Aegean region, whereas the plant with the lowest thymol content (0.25%) was *O. minutiflorum* (OMA-345) collected from Alanya. The most notable feature of *O. vulgare* (OVA-993) was its linalool content (10.17%), which was significantly higher compared to other species. The predominant components in *O. minutiflorum* essential oils, as determined by

GC-MS analysis, are carvacrol (67.86%–84.95%), p-cymene (5.36%–8.77%), and γ -terpinene (0.99%–3.46%). Other components include linalool, β -bisabolene, isoborneol, and β -caryophyllene, with thymol content ranging from 0.25% to 0.54%. In a study by Dadaloğlu and Evrendilek (2004), gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analyses identified a total of 17 components in the essential oil of thyme (*O. minutiflorum*) collected from the Aknehir district of Hatay province. The predominant components identified were carvacrol (68.23%), p-cymene (11.84%), γ -terpinene (8.14%), β -caryophyllene (3.44%), linalool (2.15%), and pinene (1.39%). As reported by Şarer et al. (1996), the essential oil of *O. minutiflorum* is

composed primarily of carvacrol (92.95%), thymol (0.25%), p-cymene (1.25%), terpineol (1.10%), and borneol (0.40%). In a subsequent study, Bardakçı and Yılmaz (2007) identified the components of *O. minutiflorum* essential oil as carvacrol (90.8%), p-cymene (2.99%), borneol (1.65%), γ -terpinene (1.18%), β -caryophyllene (1.16%), pinene (1%), myrcene (0.5%), and terpineol (0.2%). In the results of our research, the major components of *O. onites* essential oil were determined to be carvacrol (30.01%–71.96%), thymol (1.53%–38.25%), p-cymene (3.90%–10.07%), and γ -terpinene (2.25%–5.07%). Other significant components included β -bisabolene, linalool, isoborneol, and β -caryophyllene. Akgül and Bayrak (1987) identified carvacrol (74.06%), p-cymene (5.28%), terpinen-4-ol (3.10%), terpinene (2.51%), borneol (2.08%), terpinen (2.04%), linalool (1.47%), and thymol (1.36%) in *O. onites* essential oil. In a subsequent study, Azcan (1998) identified carvacrol (71.22%), thymol (5.97%), and p-cymene (4.11%) as the key components of the same species' essential oil. Ceylan et al. (1999) reported the composition of *O. onites* essential oil collected from the Muğla region as carvacrol (75.88%), cineole (7.7%), terpinene (6.84%), borneol (5.54%), and α -pinene (2.32%). In a subsequent study, Azcan et al. (2000) identified carvacrol (71.22%), thymol (5.97%), p-cymene (4.18%), γ -terpinene (2.20%), and linalool (1.74%) as the predominant components of *O. onites* essential oil. In a subsequent study, Oflaz et al. (2002) identified carvacrol (67%), p-cymene (4.5%), terpinene (4.5%), linalool (4%), and thymol (3.7%) in *O. onites* essential oil collected from the Fethiye region of Muğla. Gounaris et al. (2002) obtained essential oil from marjoram leaves, identifying carvacrol (58.73%), p-cymene (5.98%), terpinene (10%), linalool (0.2%), thymol (0.4%), and borneol (4%). In a separate study, Sokovic et al. (2002) reported carvacrol (58.6%), p-cymene (7.4%), terpinene (6.4%), α -pinene (1.7%), and borneol (4.9%) in the essential oil of the same species. In a subsequent study, Baydar et al. (2004) identified carvacrol (86.9%), terpinene

(3.9%), p-cymene (2.9%), and myrcene (1.3%) in *O. onites* essential oil. Aslım and Yücel (2007) determined the major components of *O. onites* essential oil as carvacrol (73.93%), p-cymene (7.20%), borneol (2.41%), γ -terpinene (3.99%), β -caryophyllene (1.93%), thymol (0.28%), pinene (0.18%), myrcene (0.97%), and terpineol (0.13%). The essential oil composition of *O. vulgare* samples collected from Alanya was analyzed, revealing that the main components are carvacrol (81.35%), linalool (10.17%), p-cymene (1.27%), thymol (1.21%), and β -caryophyllene (1.01%). In a separate study, Karamonoli et al. (2000) reported that the essential oil of *O. vulgare* spp. *hirtum* contained thymol (41.89%), carvacrol (19.19%), γ -terpinene (18.87%), p-cymene (4.92%), and β -myrcene (3.11%) as major components. In a subsequent study, Özcan and Akgül (2002) extracted essential oil from the leaves of *O. vulgare* and identified carvacrol (58.73%), p-cymene (5.98%), γ -terpinene (16.29%), β -caryophyllene (1.92%), linalool (1.58%), and myrcene (1.32%) as the main constituents. Esen et al. (2007) found that the essential oil of *O. vulgare* contains carvacrol (5.3–85%) and thymol (0.3–60%) as its primary components. In a separate study, Sokovic et al. (2007) reported that the essential oil of *O. vulgare* contains carvacrol (65%), p-cymene (10.9%), γ -terpinene (10.8%), β -caryophyllene (2.5%), and thymol (3.5%). Dimitrijevic et al. (2007) analyzed the essential oil of *O. vulgare* spp. *hirtum* and the analysis identified carvacrol (33.51%), spathulenol (6.2%), germacrene (6.2%), p-cymene (6.68%), thymol (5.67%), β -caryophyllene (10.29%), and linalool (3.48%) as the most significant components.

3.2. Antioxidant activity determination

The antioxidant activity of the essential oils was determined by the DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) free radical scavenging assay. The results obtained demonstrated that the *Origanum* spp. exhibited high antioxidant capacity, particularly in terms of DPPH radical scavenging activity. Among the plants studied, the essential oil with the lowest EC₅₀ value was from *O. onites* (coded OE-414) collected from

the Aegean region, while the highest value was observed in the essential oil of *O. vulgare* (coded OVA-993) collected from Alanya. In plant samples prepared as outlined in the relevant section, percentage inhibition values were determined at varying dilution rates. Linear regression analysis was employed, and the data were plotted to generate curves and their corresponding equations for each sample. Utilizing the equations of the inhibition curves, the EC₅₀ values (the concentration required to

inhibit 50% of the radicals) were calculated for each plant. The dilution process applied to the samples was also considered during the calculations. The resulting graphs were then analyzed by substituting the 50% value for the "% inhibition" value (y), and the concentration required to inhibit 50% of the radicals—essentially the antioxidant capacity of the plants—was calculated and divided by the dilution factor.

Table 5. Calculated EC₅₀ values of plant samples

Plant name	Code	EC ₅₀ Value (μL)
<i>O. minutiflorum</i>	OMA-671	3.48 ± 0.28
<i>O. onites</i>	OOA-465	1.62 ± 0.26
<i>O. minutiflorum</i>	OMA-126	1.57 ± 0.4
<i>O. minutiflorum</i>	OME-982	2.06 ± 0.11
<i>O. onites</i>	OOA-748	3.21 ± 0.34
<i>O. vulgare</i>	OVA-993	16.21 ± 0.67
<i>O. onites</i>	OOA-711	14.71 ± 1.2
<i>O. onites</i>	OOE-414	0.44 ± 0.18
<i>O. minutiflorum</i>	OMA-345	5.11 ± 0.43

An examination of Table 5 reveals that the plant with the lowest EC₅₀ value among those studied is the essential oil of *O. onites*, coded as OOE-414, which was collected from the Aegean region. Conversely, the plant with the highest EC₅₀ value is *O. vulgare*, coded as OVA-993, which was collected from Alanya.

3.3. Antimicrobial activity determination

In this study, strains of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 (ATCC 25922) and *Listeria monocytogenes* (ATCC 65031), along with their respective culture media, were utilized. The cultures were initially inoculated into tubes containing Nutrient Broth (NB) using an inoculating loop, following which they were incubated at 37 °C for activation. The resulting liquid cultures were then transferred into fresh NB tubes and incubated again at 37 °C for a period of 18–24 hours. These activated cultures were then used in inactivation studies with the plant essential oils. A significant body of research has been dedicated to investigating the antimicrobial properties of plant essential oils, emphasizing their inhibitory effects on

microbial organisms. In the present study, the essential oils obtained from the plant samples were analyzed for their antimicrobial effects on the clinical foodborne pathogens *E. coli* O157:H7 and *L. monocytogenes* using the microdilution method. The results obtained from the *Origanum* extracts tested on microorganisms indicate that the plant samples exhibited an inhibitory effect on *E. coli* O157:H7, while concomitantly reducing the count of *L. monocytogenes*. When comparing the effects of essential oils from *Origanum* species collected from different regions on the viability of *E. coli* O157:H7, the inactivation effect order was as follows: OOA-748 ≥ OMA-671 ≥ OOA-465 ≥ OMA-126 ≥ OOE-414 ≥ OVA-993 ≥ OOA-711 ≥ OMA-345 = OME-982 (P < 0.05). In a similar vein, when assessing the impact of essential oils from diverse geographical regions on the viability of *L. monocytogenes*, the inactivation effect order was determined to be: OVA-993 > OMA-126 ≥ OMA-345 ≥ OOA-711 (P < 0.05). Cosentino et al. (1999) reported that essential oils containing phenolic compounds such as p-

cymene (aromatic hydrocarbon), α -pinene and γ -terpinene (monoterpene hydrocarbons), α -terpineol and linalool (oxygenated monoterpenes), as well as thymol and carvacrol (phenolic monoterpenes) exhibit strong antimicrobial properties. It has also been reported that carvacrol and thymol, which have similar structures, demonstrate potent antimicrobial activity due to their hydroxyl groups and delocalized electrons. Research on the antimicrobial activity of thymol has demonstrated its inhibitory effect on *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *L. monocytogenes*, *P. vulgaris*, *E. aerogenes*, *S. marcescens*, and *C. albicans*. These findings contribute to the explanation of the antimicrobial activities of the essential oils tested in this study, whose main component is thymol. Research on the antimicrobial activity of carvacrol has reported its growth-inhibitory effects on *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *E. aerogenes*, *P. vulgaris*, and *C. albicans*. The findings presented herein offer valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms that underpin the pronounced antimicrobial and antioxidant activities observed in all samples characterized by elevated concentrations of carvacrol and thymol. Extensive research has previously underscored the antimicrobial properties of linalool, p-cymene, α -pinene, γ -terpinene, and borneol. The essential oils obtained from two *Origanum* species were tested against a range of bacterial and fungal strains. The bacterial strains included Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*), and Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*, *E. cloacae*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. pneumoniae*). The fungal strains included *C. albicans*, *C. tropicalis*, and *T. glabrata*. The essential oils were found to exhibit significant antibacterial and antifungal properties (Aliyiannis et al., 2001). In a study conducted by Burt and Reinders (2003), essential oils derived from four plants (*O. vulgare*, *T. vulgaris*, *P. racemosa*, and *E. caryophyllata*) were examined for their antibacterial properties, with a particular focus on their effectiveness against *E. coli*. The study revealed that essential oils from *Origanum* and *Thymus* species exhibited stronger bacteriostatic and bactericidal effects

compared to the oils from the other two plants. In a further study investigating the antimicrobial activity of essential oils obtained from six different plants, including two thyme species, the essential oils of all tested plants were isolated and evaluated against bacteria. Antimicrobial activity was observed against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *C. albicans*, while no effect was noted against *P. aeruginosa* (Lisin et al., 1999). In a subsequent study, essential oils derived from black pepper, clove, nutmeg seed, geranium, marjoram, and thyme were subjected to antimicrobial evaluation against 25 distinct bacterial genera, encompassing both animal and plant pathogens, exhibiting variable degrees of effectiveness (Dorman and Deans, 2000). An experimental study was conducted in which essential oils derived from various plant species, including *O. vulgare*, *O. dictamnus*, *O. majorana*, *T. capitatus*, *L. angustifolia*, *R. officinalis*, and *S. fruticosa*, were evaluated for their efficacy in combating the plant pathogen bacterium *C. michiganensis* spp., as well as the fungi *B. cinerea* and *F. solani* var. *coeruleum*. The study revealed that these oils significantly inhibited the growth of these pathogens (Dimitra et al., 2003). Notably, thyme exhibited a pronounced inhibitory effect against *S. aureus*, *V. parahaemolyticus*, and *S. typhimurium*. In a separate study, the effect of thyme on *Aspergillus parasiticus* NRRL 2999, an aflatoxin-producing strain, was examined. It was found that the growth of *A. parasiticus* was delayed in media containing thyme compared to media without thyme, depending on the concentration (Ova, 2001). Research indicates that the antioxidant and antimicrobial effects of *Origanum* essential oils vary. These variations may arise from the chemical composition of the plant, the type of microorganisms tested, the materials used for plant extraction, and methodological differences. As evidenced by these studies, *Origanum* species, which are widely used in traditional medicine, exhibit notable antioxidant and antimicrobial activities. The study also found that the antioxidant capacity of *Origanum* essential oils is high, suggesting their potential as alternatives to synthetic

antioxidants. Additionally, the antimicrobial activity of *Origanum* extracts against pathogenic microorganisms responsible for food spoilage was investigated. The essential oils of all three tested *Origanum* species were found to inactivate *E. coli* O157:H7 strains and reduce the counts of *L. monocytogenes* strains.

4. Conclusion

A comparison of the main components of the tested essential oils with the existing literature reveals similarities, although some differences were also observed. A plethora of studies have reported that the chemical composition and quantities of essential oils are influenced by several factors. These include the plants' genotype, chemotype, geographic origin, environmental and soil conditions, and the time of collection. Such variations in the composition of essential oils from the same plant species are commonly ascribed to factors that influence the chemical composition, biological activity, and toxicity of the essential oil. The factors under consideration encompass plant moisture, phenological stage, climate, geographic region, harvest period, distillation techniques, essential oil extraction methods, and particle size reduction (Panizzi et al., 1993). In this study, the essential oils obtained from *Origanum vulgare*, *Origanum onites*, and *Origanum minutiflorum*, collected from the Aegean and Mediterranean regions of Turkey, were analysed for their chemical composition and biological activities. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis revealed carvacrol to be the dominant compound in all three species, although its concentration varied significantly between species. *O. minutiflorum* demonstrated the highest carvacrol content, while *O. onites* exhibited a more balanced profile with notable levels of thymol and p-cymene. The antioxidant activities of the samples were evaluated using the DPPH radical scavenging assay, which revealed significant variations among the species. *O. onites* exhibited the most pronounced antioxidant activity, with an EC₅₀ value of 0.44 µL, while *O. vulgare* demonstrated the least active profile (EC₅₀: 16.21 µL). These variations may be associated with the presence

of phenolic compounds, specifically carvacrol and thymol, which have been demonstrated to possess antioxidant properties. Moreover, antimicrobial testing against *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 and *Listeria monocytogenes* demonstrated that all three *Origanum* species exhibited substantial antimicrobial properties. The essential oils demonstrated a concentration-dependent reduction in bacterial viability, underscoring their potential application as natural antimicrobial agents in food preservation and pharmaceutical contexts. In conclusion, the findings of this study contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the biological value of *Origanum* species endemic to Turkey. The results of this study highlight the significance of ecological and genetic factors in determining the chemical profile and bioactivity of essential oils. It is recommended that further studies be conducted to explore the practical applications of these oils in various industries and to gain a more profound understanding of the mechanisms behind their biological effects.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article, that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication. All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

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